

MONETARY POLICY IS THE MANAGEMENT OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE

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Abstract. In this article, the management of monetary policy in the foreign experience of the use of the effect to apply it practically giving thoughts and comments mentioned the achievements and studied Japanes.

Keywords: money and credit, finance, banking, credit, commercial bank

To enter. Monetary and financial institutions of the world economy in the activities of a great experience if you have the overall regulation of the economy with the money they have, to maintain market liquidity, payments to the effective implementation of the investment fund held for the role of complexity allows you to evaluate. The country's transition to a market economy in the context of the financial and economic stabilization to get acquainted with a number of problems both foreign experience, in particular, japan is the world most developed state of the state of the world in one example one example of the most developed in japan and known in Britain and the example of interest.

Due to the peculiarities of the historical evolution of the Uk economic and credit system is one of the world's most capitalist development. Stand out with this particular institute of high specialization.

The main part.

Government agencies had to be insignificant in comparison with other countries in the credit system of the country, for the reason that regulation of money in the economy with the role of the bank of England is of great importance. The most important objects of this regulation are the following: in accordance with the objectives of the current state policy in the economy the volume of credit

investments, the liquidity of banks and other financial institutions money market interest rates, the course of the pound sterling in the foreign exchange market, international currency and credit-financial operations.

The mechanism of the effects on the credit system of the country, the bank of England the following forms of direct and indirect intervention includes:

- some substances of commercial banks and the overall balance between the amount of a certain ratio please specify, for example, liquidity, assets and deposits the ratio between the main substance involved. This "reserve assets" in all banking institutions grows in the coefficient of 12.5% should not be lower than. In the Uk an individual bank, any own funds (capital and reserves) and the ratio between the size of deposits or credit involved or the amount given can be put on a particular loan request please keep known;
- a portion of the funds attracted by the bank of England commercial banks will require you to put in mandatory deposit. Such "special deposit" the size of from 1 to 6% varies, the amount of liquidity in the money market of the regulation of the credit and offered a quick tool. Specific requirements for all banks single norms may be supplemented with, for example, the growth of savings in the bank percent from put on a certain level of deposit;
- The change in the official rate of the bank of England, according to her account, the funds will lend to it's own homes. Weekly treasury bills rate it at the level of 0.5% of the rate is determined. If it is of such a formula of calculation adopted in October 1972, clearing the traditional deposit and loan base rate as adopted by the bank in determining the "accounting rate" to change the commanded;
- money in the open market or increase the liquidity of the market as well as reduce interest rates and money to change the mass of the relevant focused on short-term government documents (the term up to one year), buying-selling operations in the form of;

- the volume of loans of quantitative restrictions. The total amount of investment for each year until 1971 and in addition certain types of commercial bank credit to the credit limit was set. Of England recently to limit the total amount of credit the bank refused, but retained the practice of certain categories of credit limit;
- Other forms of the direct intervention of the bank of England features. For example, in connection with the sharp increase in interest rates in the year 1973-1974, the commercial bank deposits to the bank to pay more than 9.5 percent in a small form is prohibited. These restrictions are "building society" of funds from banks by increasing their rates to a decrease avoided unable to compete with the included. The direct intervention of the bank of England, the bank also 1973-1975 in the year during the crisis happened, the liquidity shortage, which is at the initiative of a number of banks who have to face the financial support of. It" redemption fund amounted to, in which the funds of the clearing bank, in addition to own funds of the bank of England led to the use of.[1]

In the UK, unlike other countries, there is no control over the monetary system from its central bank or other official bodies. Many laws that regulate the activities of the bank in the middle of the last century, including from the act of parliament, the act is adopted. The requirements for any private enterprise (except for official registration, to give balance and so on.) they control the main functions of the bank of England banking system to download. This is basically the functions of the latter "gentlemen agreements" on the basis that performs, has the power to indications that are not legitimate. This tradition of its decision to the commercial bank, the bank of England the "request" will show up in the form of supply, but they are carried out strictly on the basis of.

Global financial-economic crisis the bank of England itself during that keeps track of how interesting. Thus, in 2008, to give a bank loan UK economy out of the crisis that the country to encourage and speed up to 75 billion pounds sterling added.

Additional funds not only banks, but also to the wide sectors of the economy, is aimed at both. There is a decrease of the rate constant.

Chancellor George Os born noted of the treasury of great Britain noted the increase in the mass of money for him to be out great Britain" absolutely necessary".[2]

Increase working capital funds is based on measures proposed by the british government. The goal is to boost the economy of this growth is in: commercial bank loans, with additional funds in the financial system appear to be it is estimated that it will be ready to give.

According to the opinion of many economists in Britain associated with the production of the offered methods of pressing money, however, the UK government, according to the new banknotes does not print, but will be given the necessary funds through the purchase of securities. Similar steps were adopted in japan in the beginning of the new millennia. It is believed that the implementation of these measures gave the results slightly.

In great Britain the proposed noted analyst noted, the regulation of money and credit in strategic economic very dangerous action. Carried out in a manner sufficiently aggressive policy to increase the mass of money, this may not affect the banks and their credit ready to make.[3] with the development of such events, the financial crisis lasts long. Another potential risk or inflation gyperinflation overly active regulation of the policy implemented. Thus, the system with the bank of England conservatism on the one hand, on the second hand of the state monetary and credit policy with a small role in the installation of distinct. As for the tools, this is, in the first place, the change of the discount rate, as well as today, the crisis in the context of open market operations is approved.

The experience of Japanese economists to apply on the regulation of money and credit money and credit that can be useful in solving problems in the field of regulation of the below noted thoughts on. Japanese production of such corporation

in the decades after the war would not have the financial potential and, therefore, in the 50-60 years of the banking system played a big role in creating the conditions for the rapid growth of industry. Exactly banking institutions today, the country's economic well-being, which constitute the basis of the change of large corporations, a group of "feet to stand on" gave me the opportunity. "In japan credit-money policy" Braginskiy's the author of the book noted, noted, "only the banking system, not only using its credit funds available in the financial and entrepreneurs active in creating and house holds to collect and re-distribution, but the credit of the corporation needs to ensure that resources can be Japanese".[4]

It should be noted that after the war, almost the entire period of the banking system in japan in the working chamber was the main feature of the high level of government control. The central bank gave loans on preferential terms to private finance sector to rely on tools like the state is also effective regulation of the lending interest rates also directions, and will allow for the successful implementation of the priorities of this state is relatively. At the same time, the mechanism of such regulation in very high demand money from the financial sector the volume of credit in banks and deposit funds from going to increase the volume of on was based on a constant basis. Later, the self-financing of the corporation bank credit growth and the role of industry gradually less dependence on the corresponding administrative and credit by the central bank eventually undermine the leadership opportunities that reflect the real-money one of the reasons that the liberalization of the market has become. In the past decade, Japan's modern capital of the credit market and interest rates was the main feature of the structure strictly to regulate artificial. "In the meantime, Braginskiy noted, from the standpoint of efficiency, liberalization of interest rates in the last decade, but a large amount of bonds the structure of the state and the necessity of placing on the market and identify with the external pressure, long-term rates also credit to the present day, the market is not full".[5]

As for the monetary policy tools of the central bank of the war in Japan for the next few decades, at the rate of backup and accounting norms as well as classic as means to manipulate securities in the open market operations is of very little importance, if the credit quality from-quantitative diet on the basis of artificial low interest rate.

In recent times, the situation has been changed slightly: the decrease of the tension in the credit market of capital, its, as well as the stock market appear to be growing in see administrative regulation of the bank of Japan and significantly destroy the economic foundations of the lens of traditional, classic, forced to rethink the attitude to the means. The rate of interest rose to the level of the discount rate increased flexibility and the level of the market. Since 1971, the bills of the bank of Japan began operations in the market, while the bonds of the state structure began active operations and open them later with the transition to the subscription system. Finally, the government's short-term securities has been formed to market and other short-term mass began operations in the capital market.

Money-credit policy and the mechanism let us consider specific goals. This policy was the idea of the approach to the basis of electoral support - "artificial selection on the basis of the enterprise". The initiative was adopted by the government to conduct reforms in this area. Here I have used both bilateral decrease of interest rates and active effects: on the one hand, from the aspect administrative set at a very low level of interest rates (year from 1962 to 1977) funds in favor of the banking sector re-distribution through the collection rate increased from artificial gone, on the other hand, the shortage of capital and hence regulate the rate of credit to the central bank and the government created the credit industry and export it difficult in order to send the command to the largest corporations in the industry. Neither of the main theses of the bank of Japan conducted the policy of the government, the funds are re-distribution that arise from the unique resources that are available in the corresponding direction and directing to itself to solve the

problem for yourself is that you can leave the market process. "This is instant to the interests of the state apparatus of the initial accumulation associated excessive high v escape from a set "game rules" all the power of the force of the state to adhere to the chamber from the ability to use, 50-70 years in the country's rapid economic development has become one of the causes of the chamber and healthy."[6]

Similar features can be found in the control mechanism of the mass of money by the bank of japan. Without having to rely on indirect control, the bank primarily short-term bank lending to refer to a direct intervention in the market process. Analysis the mass of a policy to control money, "money on demand through investment mass attempts to show the effects have a limited effect when used for the prevention of the decline" can confirm the correctness of the thesis that popular. A decrease in the production of liberalization itself, whose interests and resources to deliver the stimulation of investment or credit may not be. The high level of investment demand in japan, "business confidence in the future of the economy, this high capital gains rate set". For this reason, the main purpose of credit policy in the market of credit resources, the population and distribution of lower interest small business and large corporations that are capable of carrying out effective investment of funds in favor of re-distribution was.

Select edit flow of credit in 1980, capital of monetary policy to limit the use, scale and area of the activities of financial institutions and government institutions in the area, and performed the action on the limit of macroeconomic regulation and control of attention from the gross mass requirements tend to transfer money price dynamics is observed. In such circumstances, the government began to implement economic reforms.

The government's anti-crisis measures as a result of modernization of the economy and the liberalization of the financial and economic policy, the development of market mechanisms, as well as the economy of greater "openness" and begin to be turned towards his integration into the world economy.

Taking into consideration the technical trends of the current crisis, Japan's monetary policy at the present stage of the study also should be treated.

Many developed countries like Japan also chose a way to add liquidity to the market-enhancing mass. About to give a loan to the bank of Japan 115 billion dollars allocated. The main interest rate at the same level from the low level to the left. At the same time, continues to rule in the country coming out of the sun.

The central bank of Japan, economic huge amounts of money' and decided to add a further loosening of monetary policy through.

Recently the Japanese government to the central bank in the country to take additional measures to stimulate the economy in conditions of heavy tried to pressure force.

Another important problem for the country coming out of the sun-this is enacting grow dramatically as compared to a number of dollars and other currency. Such consolidation is the decrease of income due to the latest and export of goods Japanese export to the country's economy remains significantly associated. However, the bank of Japan and the yen as investors were interested in stopping the growth of the blood of the hope of stepping on strictly has announced.

Japan central bank to commercial banks gave credit in the amount of 0.1 percent three months of the year.

The bank as a guarantee of the Japanese government bonds, commercial paper and corporate bond were used.

When the program is not time limited and should be, is cancelled by a special resolution of the bank of Japan.

The government of Japan is currently the most effective loosening of monetary policy is that it continues on enhancing liquidity in the market by providing a large amount of money at very low interest rates long-term interest rates that stimulate the decrease is more. In addition, the Japanese central bank of the year 0.1% interest rate on overnight loans which is at the level changes. For the last time in December 2008,

the bank of japan interest rate will fall to 0.1 percent per year. Before that, the central bank of japan at the end of October in seven years for the first time in the basic rate of 0.5% from 0,3% to fall. That could decrease the value of loans in the month of December after the central bank was to support the financial sector through the purchase of bank assets.

The central bank of japan, the Asia-pacific region at a time similar programs in other states realized that the strategy of minimizing the size of the injection into the economy increases. For example, the reserve bank of Australia on Tuesday for the third time since October the interest rate to 3.5% from 3,75% and expanded. Deflation lasted for 8 months in japan. In October, the consumer price fell 2.2 percent in the recession, march 2011-continued until the months of April.

Conclusion.

Unlike in the UK, the monetary system, the state of the system more relevant to the Japanese, however this does not show its effective. From the historical aspect of the conduct of monetary policy that Japanese is very soft, therefore, to stimulate economic growth in the crisis period to assume for enhancing Japan's liquidity to the market took. At the same time, the expectation of inflation is very low because deflation an integral attribute of the Japanese economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added. The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.

Used literature:

1. <http://allbest.ru/union/searchg.html>
2. <http://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki>
3. <http://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki>

4. Braginskiy S.V. Credit-japanese politik v denejnaya matter. M. INFRA 2004 g - 486 c.
5. <http://news.bbc.co.uk/hi/russian/business/newsid>
6. <http://bankir.ru/news/article>
7. Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). Fundamentals of education quality in higher education. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.
8. TOLIBJONOVICH, M. T., & OGLI, G. O. R. (2020). Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today. *JournalNX*, 6(10), 109-111.
9. Irgasheva, N., & Madaminov, K. F. N. (2020). DEVELOPING STUDENTS'MUSICAL CULTURE AND UNDERSTANDING BY LISTENING TO MUSIC. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8.
10. Madaminovich, F. Q. (2023). MUSICAL BROCHURE CREATED IN THE XI-XIII CENTURIES. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 12(06), 192-195.
11. Madaminovich, F. Q. (2023). CULTURAL DEVELOPMENT OF INDIGENOUS MUSIC. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 12(06), 184-187.
12. Tillakhujayev, O. (2022). THE SCIENCE OF MUSIC AND THE ROLE OF KNOWLEDGE OF MUSIC LYRICS IN THE FORMATION OF THE MUSICAL CULTURE OF YOUNG PEOPLE. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW* ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 175-178.

13. Tillaxo'Jayev, O. (2022). OZARBAYJON MUMTOZ MUSIQASI ORQALI O'QUVCHILARDA BAYNALMINALLIK FAZILATINI SHAKLLANTIRISH. Oriental Art and Culture, 3(4), 501-503.
14. Tillahujayev, O. T. (2023). VOKAL SAN'ATIDA PROFESSIONAL IJROGA ERISHISHDA OVOZ IMKONIYATLARIDAN FOYDALANISH TEXNIKASI. Oriental Art and Culture, 4(1), 613-621.